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COMMON TEACHING TECHNIQUES AND APPROACHES OF GRADE 4 SCIENCE TEACHERS OF BAGONG NAYON I ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN THE NEW NORMAL

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ABSTRACT

This action research aims to determine the common teaching techniques/approaches of Grade 4 Science teachers of Bagong Nayon I Elementary School during the SY 2021-2022. The researchers used the qualitative method. There were 9 teacher participants who will served as participants of the study. Since this is a basic research, no statistical treatment of data was used. Based on the recent findings, the following conclusions can be made: (1) Teachers are flexible in carrying out and utilizing approaches in their daily teaching, (2) One teacher may utilize one, two or more approaches in teaching for the welfare of the learners, (3) First-hand experience is still the best teacher among the learners, (4) Utilizing manipulatives and concrete objects in the new normal is also important, and (5) Parents and teachers should have regular communication to direct the learners. Below are the following: Teaching approaches should be shared to all teachers for the welfare of the students, One-day demonstration should be scheduled as Demo festival in Science. Encourage all Science teachers to utilize varied approaches in teaching for the welfare and interests of all learners.

Keywords: *teaching techniques, Science teachers, new normal*

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